

ACIDOID BEHAVIOUR OF CHARCOAL, AS A FUNCTION OF ITS OXYGEN COMPLEXES. PART I. ELECTROMETRIC AND CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION WITH ALKALIES

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Interaction of sugar charcoal, evacuated at increasing temperatures, with sodium hydroxide and barium hydroxide solutions was studied electrometrically as well as conductometrically, and with calcium carbonate and barium sulphide suspensions only electrometrically. The end-points of the reactions could be easily located from the titration curves. The amounts of the alkalies neutralised were found to agree with those obtained from a volumetric procedure. The values decreased on evacuating charcoal at gradually increasing temperatures. The amounts of calcium carbonate and barium sulphide decomposed by charcoal on heating under reflux were found to correspond to its acidoid value, but in closed bottles at the room temperature, the reactions took place only to the extent of about 50% and 64% respectively. During interaction with alkalies, equivalent amounts of hydroxyl and metallic ions were removed from solution, and the latter were located in the charcoal complex in exchange for its hydrogen ions.

Adsorption of acids and bases by charcoal has been the subject of several investigations (Burnstein *et al.*, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **A150**, 421; Bruns *et al.*, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, **63**, 286; Kolthoff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 4473; King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1489). Weller and Young (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 4155) have shown that the capacity of charcoal to take up bases increases with the increase in the oxygen content of its surface complex. Puri *et al.* (*Soil Sci.*, 1953, **75**, 209) regard base adsorption by charcoal as a neutralising reaction due to the presence of carbon dioxide in the surface complex. According to them charcoal containing carbon dioxide in the complex, when suspended in water, undergoes surface ionisation as

where the circle represents the charcoal surface. Because of the surface hydrogen ions being directed towards the liquid phase, charcoal behaves as a weak insoluble acid, or "acidoid" to use Michaelis terminology as applied to soils, and reacts with alkalies as

This view has received support from the measurement of heats of neutralisation of different alkalies by charcoal (Puri, Gupta and Lakhanpal, this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 219).

If the interaction of charcoal with alkalies is a neutralising reaction, as represented above, it should be possible to locate the end-point of the reaction by titrating it electrometrically as well as conductometrically against different alkalies. At the same time equivalent amounts of metal cations should be located in charcoal complex in exchange for H^+ ions.

The literature shows that titration curves of charcoal with alkalies have not been studied in details. Villars (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 214) had been perhaps the only worker to determine p_x vs. ml. of base curves in the case of carbon blacks, but as

there were no points of inflection, he concluded that these substances had no stoichiometric titre in the ordinary sense.

The present paper describes electrometric and conductometric titrations of sugar charcoal, degassed at gradually increasing temperatures, with different alkalies. The amounts of sodium and barium ions exchanged for H^+ ions during the interaction with sodium and barium hydroxides have also been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Charcoal.—Sugar charcoal obtained by the carbonisation of pure recrystallised cane sugar and exposed to oxygen at room temperature, as described in the previous work (Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1953) was used in these experiments. It was degassed at different temperatures varying from the room temperature to 900° , and the amount of CO_2 given out at each temperature was estimated by passing the gas evolved through a series of flasks containing known amounts of standard solution of barium hydroxide.

Electrometric and Conductometric Titrations.—To 0.5 g. portions of charcoal, contained in 4 oz pyrex bottles, increasing amounts of 0.1 *N*-NaOH or $Ba(OH)_2$ were added and the volume made up to 50 c.c. by the addition of distilled water. The suspensions were shaken for about 48 hours after which the p_H and conductivity values were determined by a Cambridge glass-electrode p_H -meter and a Pye bridge assembly respectively. The potentiometric and conductometric curves obtained with barium hydroxide are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively.

The electrometric curves with calcium carbonate and barium sulphide were also determined in the case of the sample degassed at room temperature. For this purpose increasing amounts of calcium carbonate and barium sulphide were added to 0.5 g. portions of the charcoal and the volume made up to 50 c.c. by the addition of distilled water. The p_H values were determined after shaking the suspensions for about 48 hours as well as after heating the same under reflux for a further period of 8 hours. The results obtained in cold as well as on heating are plotted in Fig. 3.

Volumetric Titrations.—The amount of alkali [NaOH or $Ba(OH)_2$] neutralised by charcoal was also estimated volumetrically. For this purpose, 1 g. of charcoal was shaken with 80 c.c. of 0.2 *N* alkali for about 48 hours after which the excess of alkali was determined by titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard acid solution. This method has been shown (Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1953) to give the maximum value for the capacity of charcoal to neutralise alkalies which does not increase further on prolonging the treatment or raising the concentration of the alkali solution.

DISCUSSION

The p_H -titration curves of charcoal with barium hydroxide (Fig. 1) show fairly sharp points of inflection, especially when the temperature of evacuation does not exceed 400° . The buffer capacity of charcoal is seen to decrease gradually with increase in the temperature of its evacuation. A similar curve, obtained in the case of a solution of carbon dioxide, is shown in the same figure. Its resemblance with the titration curves of charcoal is quite evident.

FIG. 2

FIG. 1

The curves obtained with sodium hydroxide show similar characteristics and are not given for reasons of space.

The conductometric curves with barium hydroxide (Fig. 2) are again quite characteristic of those of weak acids when titrated against strong alkalies. The curves obtained with sodium hydroxide have similar features and are not given for reasons of space.

The conductometric curves for dissolved CO_2 with both the alkalies are also included in Fig. 2. It is seen that the $\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3\text{—Ba(OH)}_2$ curve shows two sharp breaks on account of the precipitation of barium carbonate. However, in the case of charcoal, since the acid is not in true solution and since during the titration surface hydrogens just get replaced by barium ions in accordance with the equation given above, only one break is to be expected when, after the complete neutralisation, conductivity rises rapidly on account of the addition of free hydroxyl ions. The sodium hydroxide curve of the dissolved CO_2 shows only one break corresponding to the complete neutralisation of carbonic acid. The first break, even if obtained in this case, as mentioned by Kolthoff [*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 112, 156; although it is admitted even by him and others (Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., p. 2332) that it is difficult to get it], should not be expected in the case of charcoal since no free carbonate ions are formed (vide equation above) and the conductivity rises rapidly only when excess alkali, after complete neutralisation, is added. The analogy between charcoal and carbon dioxide is therefore limited on account of the nature of the reactions involved.

The amounts of sodium hydroxide and barium hydroxide, neutralised by the charcoal samples evacuated at different temperatures, as indicated from their electro-metric titration curves as well as from ordinary volumetric titrations, are shown in Table I. It is interesting to note that these values are in close agreement with one another irrespective of the nature of the alkali used or the method of estimation involved. This seems to offer support to the view that "base-adsorption" by charcoal is a neutralising reaction as that between an acid and a base. The amount of alkali neutralised by charcoal therefore may be termed as its "base-equivalent" or "acidoid value".

TABLE I

Interaction of sugar charcoal with alkalies on degassing at different temperatures.

Temp. of evacuation.	Alkali (m.e./100 g) required for neutralisation as determined by different methods:									
	Barium hydroxide.			Sodium hydroxide.			CaCO_3		BaS	
	E.	C.	V.	E.	C.	V.	In cold.	On heating.	In cold.	On heating.
Room temp.	550	553	556.3	559	553	555.2	259	551	358	557
100°	539	546	553.2	541	547	550.4	...	...	...	...
200°	436	438	441.6	443	439	443.5	...	...	...	...
300°	410	425	422.2	429	431	428.6	...	...	...	...
400°	315	321	325.6	329	326	328.7	...	...	...	...
500°	230	213	223.3	221	220	216.4	...	...	...	...
600°	24	26	28.3	28	33	24.4	...	...	...	...
900°	No indication		Nil	No indication		Nil	...	...	...	...

E, C and V refer respectively to Electrometric, Conductometric and Volumetric methods.

The acidoid value is seen to decrease with increase in the temperature of evacuation. This is probably due to the progressive elimination of the carbon dioxide complex at increasing temperatures. This view is confirmed by the fact that decrease in the capacity of charcoal to neutralise barium hydroxide on evacuating at a particular temperature is almost the same as the amount of CO_2 given out at that temperature, as shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Decrease in the capacity of charcoal to neutralise $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in relation to CO_2 evolved on evacuating at diff. temp.

Temp. of evacuation.	$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ neutralised by charcoal (m.e./100 g.)	Decrease in the capacity to neutralise $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ (m.e./100 g.)	CO_2 evolved on evacuating at diff. temp. (m.e./100 g.)
Room temp.	556.3	Nil	Nil
100°	553.2	3.1	Nil
200°	441.6	114.7	112.8
300°	422.2	134.1	131.8
400°	325.6	230.7	232.3
500°	223.3	333.0	332.9
600°	28.3	528.0	525.2
900°	Nil	556.3	558.0

Charcoal by virtue of its surface hydrogen ions should be able to bring about decomposition of carbonates and sulphides as well. The titration curves obtained with calcium carbonate and barium sulphide in cold (in closed vessels) as well as on heating under reflux are presented in Fig. 3. The end-point of the reaction with CaCO_3 is indicated by the curve becoming horizontal to the x-axis, i.e., any amount added in excess does not alter the p_{H} value, evidently on account of very low solubility of this substance in water. The curve with BaS , on the other hand, continues to rise because of its greater solubility in water. The point of inflection, however, can be read without much difficulty.

FIG. 3

The amounts of CaCO_3 and BaS decomposed by the charcoal (degassed at room temperature) in cold and on heating, as indicated by the titration curves, are included in Table I in appropriate column. It is seen that on heating under reflux, the amounts decomposed are quite close to the acidoid value of the charcoal, showing that the reactions take place to completion in accordance with the equations,

However, the reactions in closed bottles at the room temperature appear to stop midway on account of the fact that the gases evolved, namely CO_2 and H_2S , do not escape and so set up equilibrium conditions. In this connection it is interesting to note that under such conditions the reaction with CaCO_3 takes place to the extent of about 50% and with BaS to the extent of about 64%, in view of the fact that in the former case the same acid, namely carbonic acid, is competing for the base on either side of the equation while in the latter, the acid on the left is twice as strong as that on the right, namely, hydrogen sulphide.

TABLE III

Interaction of alkali-treated charcoal with acid solutions.

Treatment with:	NaOH-treated charcoal.				$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ -treated charcoal.			
	Decrease in the conc. of H^+ ions. (m.e./100 g.)			Sodium salt brought in soln. (m.e./100 g.)	Decrease in the conc. of H^+ ions. (m.e./100 g.)			Ba salt brought in soln. (m.e./100 g.)
	B.	C.	V.		B.	C.	V.	
HCl	545	553	551.6	549.7	531	533	541.8	536.2
H_2SO_4	548	547	546.8	547.6	...	...	...	...

If the interaction between alkalis and charcoal takes place in accordance with the above views, then an equivalent amount of the cations should be exchanged for H^+ ions on the charcoal surface. In order to verify this, 10 g. portions of the charcoal, degassed at the room temperature, were shaken with a slight excess of NaOH and $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, and after washings with distilled water, were dried in an electric oven at 110° . The amounts of sodium and barium retained on charcoal surface as a result of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{H}^+$ and $\frac{1}{2}\text{Ba}^{2+} - \text{H}^+$ exchanges were determined by titrating potentiometrically, conductometrically and volumetrically by following similar techniques, as described before, against $N/10$ solutions of HCl and H_2SO_4 (in the case of Na-charcoal only). It was found that whereas the original charcoal could adsorb no acid, the alkali-treated charcoal could remove acids in equivalent proportions (Table III) to the amounts of the alkalis neutralised by it earlier (Table I). The amounts of sodium and barium brought into solution as chlorides on treatment with dilute HCl (shaking for about 48 hours) were also determined; in the case of sodium chloride by evaporating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid to complete dryness and in the case of

barium chloride by precipitating as barium sulphate. The results are included in Table III. On comparing these values with those shown in Table I for the same sample of charcoal (degassed at room temperature), it becomes quite evident that when charcoal is treated with alkalis, both metal cations and hydroxyl anions are removed from solution in equivalent proportions in accordance with the equations given above. Bases are thus "irreversibly adsorbed" by charcoal. On subsequent treatment with acids, hydrogen ions again exchange for metal cations and charcoal regains its original capacity to react with alkalis. This perhaps can be repeated *ad infinitum*.

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